

PyProfQueue

Profiling batch jobs made easy

PyProfQueue

- Inputs:
 - .sh script
 - Queue options
 - Desired profilers
- Outputs:
 - Temp. profiling .sh script
 - Temp. work .sh script
- Once run on a cluster, outputs:
 - Files containing tracked metrics
 - Plots of the metrics

<https://github.com/uksrc-developers/PyProfQueue>

Usage


```
#!/bin/bash
```

```
#SBATCH -A example_project
```

```
#SBATCH -c 16
```

```
#SBATCH -N 1
```

```
#SBATCH -o /home/queue_work/%x.%j/output.out
```

```
#SBATCH -p example_partition
```

```
#SBATCH -J TestSubmission
```

```
#SBATCH -n 1
```

```
#SBATCH -t 00:05:00
```

```
echo "The first option was:"
```

```
echo ${1}
```

```
echo "The second option was:"
```

```
echo ${2}
```

```
import PyProfQueue as ppq

basedir = '/home/marcuskeil/Projects/RSE/Package_Development/Test/'

ProfileScript = ppq.Script(queue_system='slurm',
                            work_script=f'{basedir}slurm_test.sh',
                            read_queue_system='slurm',
                            queue_options={
                                'work_dir': f'{basedir}job_name.job_id',
                                'job_name': 'NewName'
                            },
                            profiling={
                                "likwid": {'requirements': ['module load oneAPI_comp/2021.1.0',
                                                            'module load likwid/5.2.0']},
                                "prometheus": {'requirements': ['export PROMETHEUS_SOFTWARE=/home/Software']}
                            }
                            )

ppq.submit(ProfileScript,
            tmp_work_script=f'{basedir}Example_work.sh',
            tmp_profile_script=f'{basedir}Example_slurm.sh',
            bash_options=["Hello ", "World!"],
            leave_scripts=True,
            test=True)
```

#!/bin/bash

echo "The first option was:"

echo \${1}

echo "The second option was:"

echo \${2}

```

> #!/bin/bash
#SBATCH -J NewName
#SBATCH -A example_project
#SBATCH -c 16
#SBATCH -N 1
#SBATCH -o /home/queue_work/%x.%j/output.out
#SBATCH -p example_partition
#SBATCH -n 1
#SBATCH -t 00:05:00

export WORKING_DIR=/home/marcuskeil/Projects/RSE/Package_Development/Test/${SLURM_JOB_NAME}.${SLURM_JOB_ID}
if [ ! -d "$WORKING_DIR" ]; then
    mkdir $WORKING_DIR
fi
cd $WORKING_DIR
export PYTHON_INSTANCE=/home/marcuskeil/Software/anaconda3/envs/pyprof/bin/python
# Likwid initialisation declarations
module load oneAPI_comp/2021.1.0
module load likwid/5.2.0

export LIKWID_RUNNING_DIR=${WORKING_DIR}/Likwid
mkdir $LIKWID_RUNNING_DIR

export LIK_OUTPUT=${LIKWID_RUNNING_DIR}/likwid_performance_out.txt
export THREAD_COUNT=$((($lscpu --all --parse=CPU,SOCKET,CORE | grep -v '^#' | tail -1 | grep -o -E '\.{2,3},' --max-count=1 | rev | cut -c 2- | rev) + 1))
export STREAM_SIZE=$((10 * ${THREAD_COUNT}))KB
echo 'Scalar MFlops/s' > ${LIK_OUTPUT}
likwid-bench -t peakflops -W N:${STREAM_SIZE}:${THREAD_COUNT} | grep 'MFlops/s:' >> ${LIK_OUTPUT}
echo 'SSE MFlops/s' >> ${LIK_OUTPUT}
likwid-bench -t peakflops_sse -W N:${STREAM_SIZE}:${THREAD_COUNT} | grep 'MFlops/s:' >> ${LIK_OUTPUT}
echo 'AVX MFlops/s' >> ${LIK_OUTPUT}
likwid-bench -t peakflops_avx -W N:${STREAM_SIZE}:${THREAD_COUNT} | grep 'MFlops/s:' >> ${LIK_OUTPUT}
echo 'Scalar MByte/s' >> ${LIK_OUTPUT}
export PERF=$(grep -oP 'MFlops/s:\s*\K\d+' ${LIK_OUTPUT} | sort -n | head -n 1)

likwid-bench -t load -W N:8GB:${THREAD_COUNT} | grep 'MByte/s:' >> ${LIK_OUTPUT}
echo 'SSE MByte/s' >> ${LIK_OUTPUT}
likwid-bench -t load_sse -W N:8GB:${THREAD_COUNT} | grep 'MByte/s:' >> ${LIK_OUTPUT}
echo 'AVX MByte/s' >> ${LIK_OUTPUT}
likwid-bench -t load_avx -W N:8GB:${THREAD_COUNT} | grep 'MByte/s:' >> ${LIK_OUTPUT}
export BAND=$(grep -oP 'MByte/s:\s*\K\d+' ${LIK_OUTPUT} | sort -n | head -n 1)
# Likwid initialisation done

```

```
# Prometheus initialisation declarations
export PROMETHEUS_IP=http://localhost:9090
export PROMETHEUS_SOFTWARE=/home/marcuskeil/Software/Profiling/
export PROMETHEUS_RUNNING_DIR=${WORKING_DIR}/Prometheus
export PROFILE_SCRAPE=/home/marcuskeil/Software/anaconda3/envs/pyprof/lib/python3.10/site-packages/PyProfQueue/profilers/data

mkdir ${PROMETHEUS_RUNNING_DIR}
${PROMETHEUS_SOFTWARE}/prometheus/prometheus --config.file=${PROMETHEUS_SOFTWARE}/prometheus/prometheus.yml --storage.tsdb.path=${PROMETHEUS_RUNNING_DIR}/data > /dev/null 2>&1 &
export PROMETHEUS_PID=$!
${PROMETHEUS_SOFTWARE}/node_exporter/node_exporter > /dev/null 2>&1 &
export NODE_PID=$!
# Prometheus initialisation done

export START_TIME=$(date +%s)
sleep 10

likwid-perfctr -g MEM_DP -t 300s -o ${LIKWID_RUNNING_DIR}/likwid_output.txt -O -f bash /home/marcuskeil/Projects/RSE/Package_Development/Test/Example_work.sh "Hello " "World!"

sleep 10
export END_TIME=$(date +%s)
export DURATION=$(( ${END_TIME} - ${START_TIME} ))
export START=$(date -d @${START_TIME} +"%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S")
export END=$(date -d @${END_TIME} +"%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S")

# Likwid final steps declarations
sleep 1

echo 'Plotting Likwid output as series'
${PYTHON_INSTANCE} -c "import PyProfQueue.profilers.likwid as lik;"\
"lik.plot_roof_timeseries(likwid_file='${LIKWID_RUNNING_DIR}/likwid_output.txt', "\
"name_prefix='${LIKWID_RUNNING_DIR}/Likwid', maxperf=${PERF}, maxband=${BAND})"
${PYTHON_INSTANCE} -c "import PyProfQueue.profilers.likwid as lik;"\
"lik.plot_roof_timeseries(likwid_file='${LIKWID_RUNNING_DIR}/likwid_output.txt', "\
"name_prefix='${LIKWID_RUNNING_DIR}/Likwid_Log', maxperf=${PERF}, maxband=${BAND}, log_plot=True)"# Likwid final steps done
```

```
# Prometheus final steps declarations
${PYTHON_INSTANCE} ${PROFILE_SCRAPER}/read_prometheus.py -o "${PROMETHEUS_RUNNING_DIR}" -s "${START}" -e "${END}" -i "${PROMETHEUS_IP}"
sleep 1
kill -TERM ${NODE_PID}
kill -TERM ${PROMETHEUS_PID}
echo 'Plotting Prometheus metrics to ${PROMETHEUS_RUNNING_DIR}'
if [ -f ${WORKING_DIR}/job_output_setup.txt ]; then
    ${PYTHON_INSTANCE} -c "import PyProfQueueprofilers.prometheus as prom;"\
    "df, time_series = prom.load_df('${PROMETHEUS_RUNNING_DIR}/prometheus_data');"\
    "prom.plot_prom_profiling(df=df, time_series=time_series, name_prefix='${PROMETHEUS_RUNNING_DIR}/Prometheus', "\
    "cwl_file='${WORKING_DIR}/job_output_setup.txt')"\
else
    ${PYTHON_INSTANCE} -c "import PyProfQueueprofilers.prometheus as prom;"\
    "df, time_series = prom.load_df('${PROMETHEUS_RUNNING_DIR}/prometheus_data');"\
    "prom.plot_prom_profiling(df=df, time_series=time_series, name_prefix='${PROMETHEUS_RUNNING_DIR}/Prometheus')"\
fi
# Prometheus final steps done
echo 'Run time: '$(( ${DURATION} / 60 / 60 ))': '$(( ${DURATION} / 60 % 60 ))': '$(( ${DURATION} % 60 ))'
```


Plot Examples

Prometheus

- Time-series database manager
- Node_Exporter connects to it
 - Low overhead system metric tracking
 - CPU
 - RAM
 - I/O
 - Network
- Scraping interval determines overhead cost
- Can be combined with time stamps to be used like a simple profiler

Mean CPU usage (Percentage)

- | | | | | | | |
|------------------------|------------------------------|------------------------------|----------------------------|---------------------------------|--------------------------------|--------------------------------|
| collect_linc_libraries | dp3_prep_target_39 | predict_23 | Ateamcliprar | concat_logfiles_predict_22 | concat_logfiles_clipar_4 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_22 |
| check_station_mismatch | dp3_prep_target_40 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_23 | concat_logfiles_predict | Ateamcliprar_21 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_5 | concat_logfiles_clipar_24 |
| check_ateam_separation | predict_3 | predict_22 | Ateamcliprar_4 | concat_logfiles_predict_21 | concat_logfiles_clipar_5 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_25 |
| dp3_make_parsset | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_3 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_22 | concat_logfiles_predict_4 | Ateamcliprar_24 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_6 | concat_logfiles_clipar_25 |
| dp3_prep_target | predict | predict_21 | Ateamcliprar_5 | concat_logfiles_predict_24 | concat_logfiles_clipar_2 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_26 |
| dp3_prep_target_2 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_21 | concat_logfiles_predict_5 | Ateamcliprar_25 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_3 | concat_logfiles_clipar_27 |
| dp3_prep_target_3 | predict_4 | predict_24 | Ateamcliprar_2 | concat_logfiles_predict_25 | concat_logfiles_clipar_8 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_28 |
| dp3_prep_target_4 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_4 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_24 | concat_logfiles_predict_2 | Ateamcliprar_27 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_9 | concat_logfiles_clipar_26 |
| dp3_prep_target_5 | predict_5 | predict_25 | Ateamcliprar_8 | concat_logfiles_predict_27 | concat_logfiles_clipar_7 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_27 |
| dp3_prep_target_6 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_5 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_25 | concat_logfiles_predict_8 | Ateamcliprar_26 | concat_logfiles_clipar_8 | concat_logfiles_clipar_28 |
| dp3_prep_target_7 | predict_2 | predict_27 | Ateamcliprar_7 | concat_logfiles_predict_26 | concat_logfiles_clipar_10 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_29 |
| dp3_prep_target_8 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_2 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_27 | concat_logfiles_predict_7 | concat_logfiles_predict_28 | concat_logfiles_clipar_11 | concat_logfiles_clipar_29 |
| dp3_prep_target_9 | predict_8 | predict_26 | Ateamcliprar_10 | concat_logfiles_predict_28 | concat_logfiles_clipar_6 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_30 |
| dp3_prep_target_10 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_8 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_26 | concat_logfiles_predict_10 | Ateamcliprar_29 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_7 | concat_logfiles_clipar_30 |
| dp3_prep_target_11 | predict_7 | predict_28 | Ateamcliprar_6 | concat_logfiles_predict_29 | concat_logfiles_clipar_9 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_31 |
| dp3_prep_target_12 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_7 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_28 | concat_logfiles_predict_6 | Ateamcliprar_30 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_10 | concat_logfiles_clipar_32 |
| dp3_prep_target_13 | predict_10 | predict_29 | Ateamcliprar_9 | concat_logfiles_predict_30 | concat_logfiles_clipar_11 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_33 |
| dp3_prep_target_14 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_10 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_29 | concat_logfiles_predict_9 | Ateamcliprar_32 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_12 | concat_logfiles_clipar_31 |
| dp3_prep_target_15 | predict_6 | predict_30 | Ateamcliprar_11 | concat_logfiles_predict_32 | concat_logfiles_clipar_12 | concat_logfiles_clip_A-team_32 |
| dp3_prep_target_16 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_6 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_30 | concat_logfiles_predict_11 | Ateamcliprar_31 | concat_logfiles_clipar_13 | concat_logfiles_clipar_33 |
| dp3_prep_target_17 | predict_9 | predict_32 | concat_logfiles_predict_12 | concat_logfiles_predict_31 | concat_logfiles_clipar_13 | concat_logfiles_clipar_34 |
| dp3_prep_target_18 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_9 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_32 | concat_logfiles_predict_12 | Ateamcliprar_33 | concat_logfiles_clipar_14 | concat_logfiles_clipar_34 |
| dp3_prep_target_19 | predict_11 | predict_31 | concat_logfiles_predict_13 | concat_logfiles_predict_33 | concat_logfiles_clipar_15 | concat_logfiles_clipar_35 |
| dp3_prep_target_20 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_11 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_31 | Ateamcliprar_15 | Ateamcliprar_34 | concat_logfiles_clipar_16 | concat_logfiles_clipar_35 |
| dp3_prep_target_21 | predict_12 | predict_33 | concat_logfiles_predict_15 | concat_logfiles_predict_34 | concat_logfiles_clipar_14 | concat_logfiles_clipar_36 |
| dp3_prep_target_22 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_12 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_33 | concat_logfiles_predict_14 | Ateamcliprar_35 | concat_logfiles_clipar_15 | concat_logfiles_clipar_36 |
| dp3_prep_target_23 | predict_13 | predict_34 | Ateamcliprar_14 | concat_logfiles_predict_35 | concat_logfiles_clipar_18 | concat_logfiles_clipar_37 |
| dp3_prep_target_24 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_13 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_34 | concat_logfiles_predict_18 | Ateamcliprar_36 | concat_logfiles_clipar_17 | concat_logfiles_clipar_37 |
| dp3_prep_target_25 | predict_15 | predict_35 | Ateamcliprar_18 | concat_logfiles_predict_36 | concat_logfiles_clipar_17 | concat_logfiles_clipar_38 |
| dp3_prep_target_26 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_15 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_35 | concat_logfiles_predict_17 | Ateamcliprar_37 | concat_logfiles_clipar_18 | concat_logfiles_clipar_38 |
| dp3_prep_target_27 | predict_14 | predict_36 | Ateamcliprar_17 | concat_logfiles_predict_37 | concat_logfiles_clipar_16 | concat_logfiles_clipar_39 |
| dp3_prep_target_28 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_14 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_36 | concat_logfiles_predict_17 | Ateamcliprar_38 | concat_logfiles_clipar_17 | concat_logfiles_clipar_39 |
| dp3_prep_target_29 | predict_18 | predict_37 | Ateamcliprar_16 | concat_logfiles_predict_38 | concat_logfiles_clipar_19 | concat_logfiles_clipar_39 |
| dp3_prep_target_30 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_18 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_37 | concat_logfiles_predict_16 | Ateamcliprar_39 | concat_logfiles_clipar_20 | concat_logfiles_clipar_40 |
| dp3_prep_target_31 | predict_17 | predict_38 | Ateamcliprar_19 | concat_logfiles_predict_39 | concat_logfiles_clipar_20 | concat_logfiles_clipar_41 |
| dp3_prep_target_32 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_17 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_38 | concat_logfiles_predict_19 | concat_logfiles_clipar_3 | concat_logfiles_clipar_21 | concat_logfiles_clipar_41 |
| dp3_prep_target_33 | predict_16 | predict_39 | concat_logfiles_predict_20 | concat_logfiles_clipar_3 | concat_logfiles_clipar_23 | concat_logfiles_clipar_41 |
| dp3_prep_target_34 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_16 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_39 | concat_logfiles_predict_20 | concat_logfiles_clipar | concat_logfiles_clipar_24 | concat_logfiles_clipar_41 |
| dp3_prep_target_35 | predict_19 | predict_40 | Ateamcliprar_23 | concat_logfiles_clipar_A-team_2 | concat_logfiles_clipar_22 | concat_logfiles_clipar_41 |
| dp3_prep_target_36 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_19 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_40 | concat_logfiles_predict_23 | Ateamcliprar_40 | concat_logfiles_clipar_23 | concat_logfiles_clipar_41 |
| dp3_prep_target_37 | predict_20 | Ateamcliprar_3 | Ateamcliprar_22 | concat_logfiles_predict_40 | concat_logfiles_clipar_21 | concat_logfiles_clipar_41 |
| dp3_prep_target_38 | concat_logfiles_prep_targ_20 | concat_logfiles_predict_3 | | | | |

Mean CPU usage (Percentage)

Individual CPU usage (Percentage)

RAM usage [GB]

Likwid

- Among other things can do micro-benchmarks for:
 - CPU capability
 - Memory bandwidth
- Can track “Operational Intensity” and performance
 - Operational intensity = work to be done / Memory traffic
 - FLOP/s / MBit/s
 - Performance FLOP/s
- Combine micro-benchmarks with tracking to plot Roofline model of system

Questions?

